

Demographics

- Age
- Gender
- Practice attended
- Practice Nurse or Health Promotion Coordinator arm?

		Strongly disagree	Disagree	I don't know	Agree	Strongly agree
	Scale	1	2	3	4	5
	I would like to live a healthier lifestyle					
	Scale	Not at all confident	Slightly Confident	Moderately Confident	Highly Confident	
	How confident are you that you can change your health behaviours for the better in the future?	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	

The Brief Individual Readiness for Change Scale

In the context of the areas we have spoken about during the 6 week intervention it would be good to reassess your readiness to change.

On a scale of 1-10 how ready are you right now to make a change in your lifestyle to reduce your risk of heart disease and stroke? Mark the number relevant.

Not Ready			Unsure				Ready		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

- a) How was your experience of the 'Your Heart' wellbeing program?

- What did you like about it? What did you dislike about it?
 - What encouraged you to participate in the programme?
 - Did you like that it was run in your local general practice?
 - Did you attend the programme in person or remotely? Or both? How did you like this approach?
- b) Have you ever had supports like those offered in the programme before? (e.g., have you discussed your health with health professionals before? How did the programme compare to those experiences?
- c) Did the programme help you manage your health issues? If yes/no, how so?
- d) Do you think there is a need for initiatives like this in your community?
- Would you recommend the service to a friend or family member?
 - Anything you'd change about the programme?
- e) Have you any other feedback you would like to give?